

Compounds of Metallic Salts with Organic Sulphides.

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In this annual address I would like to give a brief account of the work that is being done in my laboratory for the last few years. This deals with a study of the formation, properties and constitution of the molecular compounds of various metallic salts with organic sulphides and sulphonium halides. Reactions with salts of platinum, gold, silver, mercury, antimony, cadmium and zinc have been studied with this purpose.

Hydrochlorplatinic acid and platinum tetrahalides on treatment with mercaptans, sulphides and disulphides have been found to yield a large variety of compounds with unique properties, whose constitution it is very difficult to explain on the basis of our prevailing conceptions of valency. An explanation has been, however, suggested by the present author on the assumption of variability of the valency of platinum combined with the tendency of the sulphur atom of the sulphides and disulphides to form sulphonium derivatives (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 178, 329; 1930, 187, 33; 1931, 198, 53). This tendency of the sulphur atom, as we shall presently see, may be regarded as the underlying "motif" in the formation of many of these molecular compounds of metallic salts with organic thio-compounds. In others, the existence of double or complex compounds of metallic salts with the corresponding sulphonium salts, have been proved, the sulphonium salts being formed during the course of the reaction.

By the interaction of alkyl sulphide, disulphide or trisulphide with ethyl iodide and mercuric iodide, compounds of the type $R_3SI \cdot HgI_2$ and $2 R_3SI \cdot HgI_2$ (where $R = CH_3, C_2H_5$ etc.) have been prepared (Rây and Adhikary, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 297; Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 163; 1907, 91, 1397). These are evidently complex compounds of the type $KHgI_3$ and K_2HgI_4 and should be represented as $R_3S \cdot HgI_3$ and $(R_3S)_2 \cdot HgI_4$. This has been verified by their preparation directly from R_3SI and

HgI_2 , as well as by the measurements of their conductivity in acetone solutions (*cf.* Rây, *loc. cit.*).

Hydrochlor-auric acid and auric chloride react with mercaptans and sulphides leading, however, to the formation of additive compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ (R = alkyl radicle) (Philips, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 23, 257; Rây and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 67). Similarly alkyl sulphides and disulphides react with silver nitrate giving rise to compounds of the type $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}_2$.

Cadmium and zinc behave like mercury and yield, when their iodides are allowed to react with alkyl sulphides or disulphides and alkyl iodides, compounds of the types $(\text{R}_3\text{S}) \cdot \text{MI}_3$ and $(\text{R}_3\text{S})_2 \cdot \text{MI}_4$, where R_3 is either simple or mixed alkyl radicle and M is Cd or Zn (Rây, Adhikari and Banerjee—paper communicated to the Indian Chemical Society). In addition to these two types, zinc forms a compound of the type $\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{S}\}_4 \cdot \text{ZnI}_6$. They are in fact, strictly comparable to KCdI_3 and K_2CdI_4 .

Antimony halides have been found to react with alkyl sulphides and alkyl halides giving a large number of compounds of the type $\text{SbX}_3 \cdot \text{R}_3\text{SX}$ or $\text{R}_3\text{S} \cdot \text{SbX}_4$, besides a compound of the type $(\text{R}_3\text{S})_3 \cdot \text{SbX}_6$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$, Br , or I and $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ or C_2H_5 (*cf.* Rây, Adhikari and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 251). That these compounds represent true complexes of the Werner type is proved by the results of their conductivity measurements and specially by the fact that identical compounds $\{(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{S}\}_3 \cdot \text{SbBr}_3\text{I}_3$ is obtained when either (i) SbI_3 is treated with excess of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{SBr}$, or (ii) SbBr_3 is made to react with an excess of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{SI}$. In the event of their being merely additive compounds, two different products, namely, $\text{SbI}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_3\text{SBr}$ and $\text{SbBr}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_3\text{SI}$ would have resulted. The identity of these two compounds has been established from a study of their physical and chemical properties (Rây, *loc. cit.*). The results are in perfect agreement with Atkinson's observation regarding the reactions between KCl and SbBr_3 on the one hand, and KBr and SbCl_3 on the other, the identical product $\text{K}_3(\text{SbCl}_3\text{Br}_3)$ being obtained in both cases (*Chem. News*, 1883, 47, 175; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 291).

Antimony trichloride also reacts with alkyl sulphides yielding compounds of the type $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ and $4\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{R}_2\text{S}$, where R is an alkyl radicle. Some of these compounds, when heated in alcoholic solution, decompose and lead to the formation of compounds

of the type $2\text{SbCl}_3\text{HCl}\cdot 3\text{R}_2\text{S}$. The constitution of these compounds presents certain very interesting features. When compounds of the type, $\text{SbCl}_3\cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ is treated with water no oxychloride is precipitated unlike the simple antimony salts; on the other hand, the bulk of the compound is decomposed with the formation of orange antimony sulphide. Since no antimony sulphide is produced when a simple mixture of SbCl_3 and Et_2S is heated with water, it definitely indicates that in the compound $\text{SbCl}_3\text{—Et}_2\text{S}$ the sulphur atom is directly linked to the metallic atom of antimony. The product should, therefore, be represented as a sulphonium compound of the constitution

and be expected to behave as a strong binary electrolyte like the simple sulphonium salts. This has been strikingly verified by the conductivity and ebullioscopic measurements in acetone solution of the substance. SbCl_3 in acetone solution is practically a non-electrolyte, whereas the above compound in the same solution behaves as a binary electrolyte. The molecular weight of the substance in acetone, determined from the elevation of boiling point of the latter is approximately half the value calculated from its formula. This establishes, beyond doubt, the above view of its constitution.

This sulphonium nature of its constitution promises a new and very interesting line of work on the subject. If, in place of a simple sulphide like Et_2S , a mixed sulphide of the type $\begin{array}{l} \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array} \text{S}$ be substituted, it can be easily observed that the compound formed would be resolvable into its optically active antipodes, the sulphur being asymmetrical under this condition. This is evident from the following constitutional formula

Work in this line is in progress.

With the exception of the antimony derivatives, all other above described compounds of metallic salts with organic sulphides,

when treated with dry ammonia, exchange their alkyl sulphide group with ammonia and the corresponding ammoniated metallic salts are formed. In the case of antimony compounds, however, the latter are decomposed by ammonia with the formation of antimony sulphide. This furnishes an additional evidence in favour of the sulphonium constitution of the compounds of the antimony halides with organic sulphides.

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